

Human Rights in Nepal's Democracy: Achieving Best Practices

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Suggested Citation

Guragain, J.P., Kafle, D.R., Mallik, S.K., & Adhikari, B.S. (2024). Human Rights in Nepal's Democracy: Achieving Best Practices. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(4), 237-247.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(4\).20](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(4).20)

Abstract:

This article outlines the status of human rights practices and provisions within Nepal, a democratic nation where democracy, progress, and the rule of law are interconnected with the preservation of human rights and fundamental freedoms. Nepal, as a democracy, ensures the protection of human rights for its citizens. Over the past few decades, significant strides have been made in enhancing these practices and provisions, particularly in granting rights to marginalized groups as per the 2015 Constitution. However, despite these advancements, the Nepalese government has consistently overlooked recommendations from the Commission to investigate

and prosecute human rights violations, as mandated by the Constitution. There is a need for the Nepalese government to prioritize the human rights movement, which faces numerous challenges from activities that contradict the principles of the constitution, democratic norms, and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The paper highlights progress in human rights provisions and practices, alongside suggestions to actively ratify the Rome Statute to enhance Nepal's international reputation.

Keywords: *Constitution, Democracy, Human Rights, Provisions, Violations.*

Introduction

The United Nations has defined human rights as the inherent entitlements of every individual, irrespective of factors such as race, gender, nationality, language, religion, or any other status. These rights encompass essential liberties such as the right to life and freedom, protection against slavery and torture, freedom of expression and

opinion, as well as access to work and education, among others. They are universally applicable, without any form of discrimination. International human rights law outlines the responsibilities of governments to uphold and protect these rights, including specific actions to be taken or avoided. The development of a comprehensive body of human rights law, endorsed globally and internationally upheld, stands as a significant

achievement of the United Nations. This framework encompasses a broad spectrum of rights, including civil, cultural, economic, political, and social rights, and is supported by mechanisms aimed at promoting and safeguarding these rights, while assisting states in fulfilling their obligations.

The principles of democracy and human rights are built upon common values such as accountability, personal freedom, integrity, fair representation, inclusivity, participation, and peaceful conflict resolution. Contemporary understandings of democracy rest on core principles of popular sovereignty and collaborative decision-making, where leaders are answerable to their constituents through various mechanisms (Beetham & International Institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance, 2008).

Democracy, as a system of governance, serves as a universal standard for safeguarding human rights, fostering an environment conducive to their protection and fulfilment. Despite a previous trend of widespread democratization globally, numerous democracies are currently experiencing setbacks. Certain governments are actively diminishing independent oversight of their authority, suppressing dissent, undermining democratic accountability, and consolidating long-term control, resulting in adverse effects on individuals' rights (OHCHR | About Democracy and Human Rights, n.d.).

Human rights preservation is not a hindrance but a necessity for a functioning democracy. Human rights guarantee impartiality in elections, facilitate transparent communication, and foster fair decision-making processes. They ensure the implementation of democratic choices, enhancing the efficiency of democratic governance. By safeguarding the rights of individuals and minorities, human rights prevent the tyranny of the majority and enable diverse voices to be heard within the democratic framework. In a democracy, human rights ensure that even minority interests are protected. The flourishing of human rights is closely intertwined with the success of democracy, as both are essential for individual and collective self-determination. Therefore, human rights protection and realization are integral

components of a truly democratic endeavor (Why Democracy and Human Rights Are Two Sides of the Same Coin, 2019). The inception of human rights is often attributed to the Magna Carta, also known as the Charter of British Civil Rights, dating back to 1215 AD. This historic document emerged from an agreement between King John of Britain and the populace, outlining the distribution of authority and acknowledging the rights of the people. The Magna Carta is recognized as the earliest written instrument delineating human rights. It affirmed Parliament's authority to enact laws, restricted the king's ability to levy taxes without parliamentary consent, and advocated for the establishment of an independent judiciary and the rule of law.

After a prolonged struggle between the monarchy and the British populace, the "Bill of Privileges" emerged in 1689 as a means to delineate and constrain the king's authority, marking the monarch's inaugural social compact with the people. Similarly, in 1776 AD, the United States of America issued the "Declaration of American Independence," drawing inspiration from the fundamental principles of the British "Bill of Rights." Likewise, the French Revolution, culminating in 1779, was driven by the conviction that every individual possesses the right to liberty and self-governance. The foundational concept of human rights was further solidified through the declaration of the rights of man and citizen, formally adopted by the French National Assembly in 1789. Established on January 10, 1920, the League of Nations was formed with the aim of addressing concerns that escalating antagonism and competition among nations could endanger human rights, despite significant international strides toward human rights advancement in the eighteenth century. It adopted policies of non-discrimination based on race, religion, language, or gender. However, preceding endeavors to promote human rights and peace proved ineffective following the aftermath of two global conflicts: World War I (1914-1918) and World War II (1939-1945). Each individual bears the responsibility to uphold and cherish the rights of others. The

United Nations (UN) was founded on October 24, 1945, as a response to the imperative for a global entity to guide the entire international community in embracing and safeguarding the core principles of unity, peace, and mutual coexistence in the wake of two devastating world wars. Subsequently, there emerged a resolute and coordinated effort to advance peace and human rights.

Shortly after its inception, in the early months of 1946, the United Nations (UN) undertook the initiative to establish the Human Rights Commission, aiming to enhance and specify provisions for the promotion of human rights. By 1947, the Commission had drafted the International Bill of Human Rights in accordance with the principles outlined in the United Nations Charter. On December 10, 1948, the UN General Assembly adopted the document as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR).

The UN General Assembly also emphasizes the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) as a unified pathway for progress applicable to all individuals and nations. It aims for every person and societal institution to strive, through education and awareness, to bolster respect for these rights and freedoms outlined in the Declaration. Furthermore, it advocates for the implementation of continuous national and international measures to ensure the universal acknowledgment and enforcement of these rights and liberties among both individuals and nations. In this context, Human Rights are delineated as inherent and indivisible entitlements pertaining to life, liberty, and the pursuit of happiness, a concept also enshrined in the American Constitution. Lohani et al. (1998) elucidate that Martin Luther King Jr., a clergyman and civil rights activist, delivered a seminal political address titled "I Have a Dream," advocating for universal human rights. On August 28, 1963, in Washington D.C., King's non-violent resistance movement reached a historic apex as he led a march of 200,000 individuals—both black and white—from the Washington Monument to the Lincoln Memorial, coinciding with the centennial of Lincoln's Emancipation Proclamation. Before

this vast audience, and to millions watching on television, King delivered a memorable speech championing human rights and advocating for equality for black individuals alongside white counterparts. Similarly, in his 1963 speech "I Have a Dream," King identified basic human rights as the "unalienable rights of life, liberty, and the pursuit of happiness," asserting that these fundamental rights should be universally applied to all citizens worldwide. The human rights enshrined in the Nepalese constitution are likely to align with the fundamental rights of life, liberty, and the pursuit of happiness as articulated in the American constitution.

Research Questions

- A. How is the state of human rights practice in Nepal?
- B. What are the provisions of human rights for the deprived groups mentioned in the constitution of Nepal?
- C. What are the human rights challenges in Nepal?

Objectives of the Study

- A. To understand the state of human rights practice in Nepal.
- B. To explore the human rights provided to the deprived groups.
- C. To unravel the human rights challenges in Nepal.

Methodology of the Study

This study is primarily a critical examination of Nepal's human rights practices and provisions, utilizing secondary data sourced from various national and international publications and online platforms. The secondary data collection process involved reviewing relevant papers, policy documents, journal articles, books, and other significant sources available in both Nepali and English languages. Additionally, the material includes insights from numerous articles, seminar papers, and reports issued by national and international organizations.

Delimitation

This study focuses on the diverse human rights practices within the democratic nation of Nepal and may not be directly applicable to other countries. It specifically addresses certain human rights issues affecting marginalized groups within Nepal. The findings presented in this study are primarily derived from extensive literature reviews, with a significant emphasis on the Constitution of Nepal.

Literature Review

Limited efforts have been undertaken to investigate Nepal's human rights situation, while globally, there have been endeavors to study human rights practices. An international book titled "The Practice of Human Rights" examines the evolution of human rights practices within the United Nations. It emphasizes the global nature of human rights from a conceptual or philosophical perspective, a notion that is acknowledged but may hold marginal significance for anthropologists and other researchers studying human rights as a prominent contemporary international discourse. The book primarily delves into the importance of anthropological discussions surrounding human rights discourse and its impact on local social and political contexts. It suggests that anthropologists should engage with the venues where international human rights legislation and norms are formulated, and gain access to international criminal tribunals to assess their knowledge formation processes (Goodale & Merry, 2007). Moreover, Sanford A. Lakoff has conducted research on human rights and democratic endeavors aimed at promoting democratic governance and human rights as essential elements for sustainable development in developing nations. Furthermore, he explores the evolution of human rights alongside the establishment of democratic nations and their developmental phases. This research underscores the significance of understanding the origins and evolution of the doctrine of human rights, as it is integral to comprehending and embracing democracy. Lakoff emphasizes the urgent need for a thorough understanding or reinterpretation

of this idea due to its critical importance in contemporary discourse (Lakoff, 1991). Similarly, Hun Joon Kim has shed light on the structural factors influencing human rights prosecutions following democratic transitions. This article explores three key theories in response to the ongoing criminal trials of former state leaders accused of human rights violations: the power dynamics between old and new elites, international advocacy networks, and the diffusion theory (Kim, 2012).

Result and Analysis of Human Rights Practices

Democracy, progress, the rule of law, and the safeguarding of human rights and fundamental freedoms are interconnected and mutually reinforcing. Governments, intergovernmental organizations, and non-governmental organizations increasingly emphasize that democracy is not only a goal in itself but also a crucial component for achieving other objectives, such as economic growth, reform, and the protection of human rights and freedoms.

For many years, the UN General Assembly and the former Commission on Human Rights worked to establish a common understanding of the principles and goals of democracy, drawing from international human rights instruments. In 2002, the Commission affirmed in Resolution 2002/46 that respecting human rights and fundamental freedoms, particularly freedom of thought, speech, and association, are essential elements of democracy (OHCHR | About Democracy and Human Rights, n.d.).

Nepal has made progress in human rights provisions and practices as a democratic nation, ensuring rights to its citizens. However, Prime Minister K.P. Oli's government has introduced new legislation restricting freedom of expression while failing to address past violations during the civil war that ended in 2006. There is a continued prioritization of impunity for criminals, including security officials and members of the ruling Nepal Communist Party, over justice for victims. Alleged extrajudicial killings by security

forces and deaths in custody due to torture have not been adequately investigated. Marginalized castes and ethnic groups are particularly susceptible to abuse.

Several laws currently under consideration by parliament pose threats to freedom of expression, with punitive measures for vaguely defined offenses related to media and online communication. Other proposed legislation grants broad search and surveillance powers to the intelligence service and curtails the authority of the National Human Rights Commission. A citizenship bill maintains clauses limiting women's ability to confer citizenship to their children or spouse. While the legislation may aid certain individuals at risk of statelessness, such as orphans with unrecognized parents, it raises concerns about the erosion of rights and freedoms (Human Rights Watch, 2021). The section on 'Fundamental Rights and Duties (Part 3, Articles 16-46)' in Nepal's 2015 Constitution aligns with the core human rights outlined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, as well as international humanitarian law and human rights mechanisms. Article 16 of this Constitution guarantees the right to life for every individual and explicitly prohibits the adoption of laws pertaining to the death penalty. Similarly, Article 17 ensures that no person shall be deprived of personal liberty, except in situations sanctioned by law, and encompasses freedoms such as expression, peaceful assembly without arms, establishment of organizations, residency and movement within the country, employment rights, and the establishment and operation of businesses and professional ventures nationwide.

Freedom of Expression

Several legislative proposals introduced in parliament have advocated for significant restrictions on freedom of expression. In May, the Upper House approved a new Special Service Bill, granting the National Investigation Department (NID), Nepal's spy agency, expanded powers to monitor communications and conduct asset inspections without judicial oversight. Additionally, other bills currently under consideration by parliament, including the

Media Council Bill, the Information Technology Bill, and the Mass Communications Bill, contain a range of stringent measures aimed at controlling mainstream media and curtailing freedom of expression for journalists and social media users. These bills propose harsh penalties, including custodial sentences, for individuals who violate broad and ambiguous prohibitions, particularly related to the subjects mentioned.

Women's Rights

Both the Citizenship Act of 2006 and Nepal's 2015 constitution contain provisions that discriminate against women. Despite efforts to amend discriminatory elements, a proposed citizenship bill that progressed through the parliamentary committee stage in June retained some discriminatory clauses. In response, three UN human rights experts expressed concern in September that "the bill would perpetuate systematic discrimination against women, particularly regarding their ability to pass on citizenship through marriage and to their children." Legal shortcomings and a lack of political resolve have hindered accountability for sexual violence, especially for victims from marginalized communities. A one-year statute of limitations on rape and sexual abuse allegations prevents many cases from being prosecuted. Amendments were made to enhance punishment for perpetrators of acid attacks and to regulate the sale of acid.

The constitution of Nepal guarantees women the right to safe motherhood and reproductive health, and prohibits any form of violence or exploitation against women based on religion, social, cultural practices, or other grounds. Despite legislative efforts and initiatives to prevent child marriage, the practice persists, with 7% of girls married before the age of 15 and 40% married by the age of 18. Conversely, by the age of 18, 10% of boys are married.

Gender Identity

The 2015 constitution of Nepal acknowledges a third gender and safeguards the rights of "gender and sexual minorities" within sections pertaining to equality before the law and social justice. The Supreme Court has officially recognized a third

gender category, allowing individuals to self-identify. However, a proposed citizenship law would require the presentation of a medical certificate to select the "other" gender category. In 2007, the Supreme Court directed a study on equal marriage rights for same-sex couples, yet the 2018 criminal code only recognizes marriages between men and women.

Rights for Minorities

UN High Commissioner for Human Rights Michelle Bachelet stated that despite constitutional protections, impunity for caste-based discrimination and violence persists in Nepal. The 2015 constitution of Nepal established separate commissions to protect the rights of marginalized groups such as Dalits, Tharus, Muslims, Madhesis, and indigenous peoples, aiming to promote inclusivity. However, the government has largely failed to adequately staff and empower these commissions, rendering them largely ineffective.

Rights to Truth, Justice and Reparation

During the 1996-2006 conflict, the government failed to address the needs of tens of thousands of victims of international law crimes and other serious human rights violations, neglecting to provide truth, justice, and restitution. Despite receiving over 60,000 complaints from victims, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission and the Commission of Investigation on Enforced Disappeared Persons were unable to resolve any cases. The government has yet to amend the Investigation of Enforced Disappeared Persons, Truth and Reconciliation Commission Act of 2014, as directed by the Supreme Court in 2014 and 2015, to align it with Nepali and international human rights standards. The administration extended the tenure of both commissions in July.

Rights and Duties

Nepal's Constitution of 2072 B.S. outlines the Rights and Obligations of citizens in Part 3, starting from number sixteen. It includes provisions such as the Right to a dignified life, which ensures every individual's entitlement to live with dignity and prohibits the imposition of the death penalty by legislation. Additionally, it

guarantees the Right to freedom, stating that no person shall be deprived of their personal liberty except as per the law. Every citizen is granted various freedoms, including freedom of opinion and expression, peaceful assembly, formation of political parties, unions, and associations, freedom of movement and residence within Nepal, and freedom to practice any profession or trade. However, reasonable restrictions may be imposed by law to prevent actions that undermine Nepal's sovereignty, territorial integrity, nationality, or harm relations between Federal Units, castes, tribes, religions, or communities.

This includes actions such as inciting caste-based discrimination or untouchability, disrespecting labor, defaming others, showing contempt for the court, inciting offenses, or behaving contrary to public decency or morality. Sub-clause (b) allows for the enactment of laws to impose reasonable restrictions on actions that undermine sovereignty, territorial integrity, nationality, independence, or public peace and order. Sub-clause (c) permits the creation of laws to impose reasonable restrictions on actions that undermine Nepal's sovereignty, territorial integrity, nationality, or constitute espionage against the nation. Sub-clause (d) enables the formulation of laws to impose reasonable restrictions on actions that undermine Nepal's sovereignty, territorial integrity, nationality, or constitute espionage against the nation. Sub-clause (e) allows for the establishment of laws to impose reasonable restrictions on actions that undermine the interest of the general public or harmonious relations between Federal Units or various castes, tribes, religions, or communities. Sub-clause (f) permits the creation of laws to prevent actions that undermine harmonious relations between Federal Units or actions contrary to public health, decency, or morality.

This includes granting the State exclusive authority to engage in specific industries, trades, or services and establishing criteria or qualifications for engaging in any industry, trade, occupation, employment, or business.

Regarding the right to equality:

1. All citizens are equal under the law, and no individual shall be deprived of equal protection by the law.

2. General laws must not discriminate based on factors such as origin, religion, race, caste, tribe, sex, physical condition, health status, marital status, pregnancy, economic status, language, region, ideology, or similar characteristics.

3. The State is prohibited from discriminating against citizens on the basis of factors such as origin, religion, race, caste, tribe, sex, economic status, language, region, ideology, or similar characteristics. However, laws may be enacted to provide special provisions for the protection, empowerment, or advancement of socially or culturally disadvantaged groups, including women, Dalits, indigenous peoples, Madhesis, Tharus, Muslims, oppressed classes, backward classes, minorities, marginalized communities, farmers, laborers, youth, children, senior citizens, gender and sexual minorities, persons with disabilities, pregnant individuals, incapacitated or vulnerable individuals, underdeveloped regions, and economically disadvantaged Khas Arya. Additionally:

- Gender-based discrimination in terms of remuneration and social security for the same work is prohibited.
- All offspring have equal rights to ancestral property without regard to gender.
- Regarding the right to communication:
- No censorship shall be enforced on the publication, broadcasting, dissemination, or printing of any news, editorial, feature article, or other content via any means, including electronic platforms.

However, laws may impose reasonable restrictions on activities that undermine Nepal's sovereignty, territorial integrity, nationality, or peaceful relations between federal units, castes, tribes, religions, or communities. Such restrictions include actions like sedition, defamation, contempt of court, incitement to commit a crime, or behaviors contrary to public decency or morality, as well as those promoting hatred towards labor, caste-based untouchability, or gender discrimination.

Furthermore:

- No radio, television, online, or other digital or electronic media, including the press, shall be closed, seized, or have its registration canceled solely due to the use of audio, audio-visual, or electronic equipment. However, the law may regulate these media outlets.
- Communication means, such as the press, electronic broadcasting, and telephones, shall not be interrupted except in accordance with the law.

Regarding rights related to justice:

- No individual shall be detained without being informed of the reasons for their arrest.
- Any arrested person has the right to consult a legal practitioner of their choice from the moment of arrest and to be represented by such a legal practitioner. Conversations and advice with the legal practitioner are confidential, except for citizens of enemy states.

Explanation: The term "Legal practitioner" refers to any individual authorized by law to represent someone in any court of law.

Any individual who is arrested must be brought before the adjudicating authority within twenty-four hours of their arrest, excluding the time required for transportation from the place of arrest to the authority. Detention cannot occur without the authorization of this authority, except in cases of preventive detention and for citizens of enemy states.

No individual shall be punished for an act that was not considered punishable by the law at the time the act was committed. Moreover, no individual shall face a punishment greater than that prescribed by the law in force at the time of the offense. Every person accused of a crime is presumed innocent until proven guilty, and no person shall be tried and punished for the same offense more than once.

Additionally:

- No person charged with an offense shall be compelled to testify against themselves.

- Every person has the right to be informed of any legal proceedings taken against them.
- Every person is entitled to a fair trial by an independent, impartial, and competent court or judicial body.
- Any party who is unable to afford legal representation has the right to free legal aid according to the law.

Regarding the rights of crime victims:

- Victims of crimes have the right to information about the investigation and legal proceedings of the case in which they are victims.
- Crime victims have the right to justice, including social rehabilitation and compensation, as provided by the law.

Furthermore:

- No individual who is arrested or detained shall be subjected to physical or mental torture or cruel, inhuman, or degrading treatment. Acts mentioned in this clause are punishable by law, and victims have the right to obtain compensation according to legal provisions.
- No person shall be held under preventive detention unless there is sufficient evidence of an immediate threat to the sovereignty, territorial integrity, or public peace and order of Nepal. Information about the status of a person under preventive detention must be immediately provided to their family (Nepal's Constitution, 2072 B.S.). The provisions outlined in Nepal's Constitution serve to legally ensure fundamental rights for its citizens, aligning with the principles of human rights as declared by the United Nations. However, despite these legal safeguards, Nepal faces numerous challenges in effectively upholding human rights.

While the constitution provides a framework for protecting citizens' fundamental rights, the implementation of these rights often falls short due to various obstacles. These challenges may include bureaucratic inefficiencies, inadequate enforcement mechanisms, systemic discrimination, and socio-cultural barriers.

Additionally, political instability, corruption, and resource constraints can further hinder efforts to safeguard human rights.

Despite efforts to align national laws with international human rights standards, there may be discrepancies between legal frameworks and their practical application. This can result in marginalized groups, such as women, minorities, and vulnerable populations, facing systemic discrimination and violations of their rights.

Furthermore, issues such as impunity for human rights abuses, limited access to justice, and lack of accountability mechanisms contribute to a culture of impunity and undermine public trust in the government's commitment to upholding human rights.

Addressing these challenges requires concerted efforts from the government, civil society organizations, and the international community. It involves strengthening legal frameworks, enhancing institutional capacity, promoting awareness and education on human rights, and fostering a culture of respect for human dignity and equality.

Overall, while Nepal's constitution provides a foundation for protecting fundamental rights, addressing the challenges to effective human rights implementation remains an ongoing endeavor that requires sustained commitment and collaboration from all stakeholders involved.

Human Rights Challenges in Nepal

Following the political upheaval of 1950-51, which marked the end of the century-old Rana government, there was a notable improvement in Nepal's human rights situation. However, subsequent political events posed significant challenges to further progress in this area. These events included the royal coup against the democratically elected government in 1960, the prolonged authoritarian rule of the Panchayat system for three decades, the King's unilateral actions on February 1, 2005, and the decade-long Maoist insurgency from 1996 to 2006.

The restoration of democracy in Nepal, triggered by the National People's Movement of 1990 and the People's Movement of 2006, created a

conducive environment for enhancing the country's human rights landscape. Additionally, the adoption of Nepal's Constitution by the Constituent Assembly in 2015 marked a positive milestone in safeguarding human rights principles and practices within the nation.

However, despite these advancements, it would be premature to assert that Nepal's human rights situation is devoid of threats. Various factors, including political instability, ethnic tensions, socio-economic disparities, and challenges in implementing legal frameworks, continue to pose obstacles to the full realization of human rights in the country.

Moving forward, sustained efforts are required to address these challenges comprehensively. This entails strengthening democratic institutions, ensuring the rule of law, promoting social inclusion and equality, combating impunity for human rights violations, and fostering a culture of respect for human dignity and rights for all citizens of Nepal. Part 25, Articles 248 and 249 of the Nepalese Constitution outline the formation of the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC), which is tasked with conducting inquiries and investigations into human rights violations and proposing measures against those responsible (*Nepal_2015.Pdf*, n.d.).

However, the Nepalese government consistently disregards the recommendations of the Commission to investigate and prosecute human rights violations in accordance with the Constitution's requirements. This ongoing situation has become a major barrier to Nepal's efforts to protect and uphold human rights, revealing the government's lack of genuine commitment to addressing human rights issues.

Part 25 of the Nepalese constitution outlines the essential provisions regarding the National Human Rights Commission. It delineates the establishment and operational guidelines for the National Human Rights Commission in Nepal. The Commission consists of a chairperson and four members, appointed by the President upon the recommendation of the Constitutional Council. Their term spans six years, and reappointment is prohibited, except for a

member who may be appointed as the Chairperson. Vacancies occur through resignation, impeachment, removal due to incapacity, or death. Eligibility criteria for the Chairperson and members include relevant qualifications, age, moral integrity, and not being affiliated with any political party at the time of appointment. Their remuneration and service conditions are determined by federal law, with no alterations to their detriment during their tenure, except in a state of emergency caused by severe economic crises. Once appointed, individuals cannot take up other government service roles, except for political or investigative positions. The functions of the National Human Rights Commission include safeguarding, promoting, and enforcing human rights. It investigates complaints, recommends actions against violators, addresses failures in preventing violations, recommends legal action, collaborates with civil society, reviews human rights laws, recommends treaty adherence, and monitors implementation. The Commission also has powers similar to a court, such as summoning individuals, conducting searches, and providing compensation to victims. Delegation of functions to specific individuals and other details are outlined in federal law (Nepal's Constitution 2072). This provision of the National Human Rights Commission has guaranteed to enact the Fundamental Human Rights to all the citizens as well as the foreigners who happen to be in the democratic country, Nepal. Adhikari et al (2022) have pointed out their views about the human rights and the joint effort for the establishing global peace and ecofriendly activities for the rights of the coexistence on the healthy and sound earth. Likewise, Adhikari (2020) has argued that it has become essential for the maintaining of the ecology and environment of the world for the existence of human life as their fundamental rights. Furthermore, Adhikari et al (2020) have pointed out about the need of conserving the environment of the world and its initiation has become from Nepal by starting the act of preservation of the vultures from the small rural area of Sunsari district, the eastern part of Nepal by collecting and keeping the carcasses in a restaurant of the vulture and it has become a

kind of activity related with the human rights of survival by protecting the life of others simultaneously.

Conclusion

Despite widespread public support, the prevailing majority government's adverse stance and actions have emerged as substantial barriers to achieving peace and upholding human rights. The human rights movement is encountering formidable challenges due to numerous activities that run counter to the fundamental essence of the constitution, democratic principles, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, and the sentiments expressed by the electorate during elections. The government's mindset and objectives have been laid bare by its insistence on introducing certain bills, which were ultimately withdrawn following widespread public outcry: (i) the Media Council Bill, which contradicts both the letter and spirit of the constitution, including the principles and norms underpinning universal press freedom; (ii) the Guthi Bill, which diverges from the cultural values and long-standing traditions cherished by the populace (subsequently retracted due to public pressure); and (iii) the Constitutional Council Bill, which sought to subordinate the Council fully to the government, contravening the spirit of the Constitution. As a consequence of the government's stance and actions, the progress of human rights and democracy has encountered significant impediments.

Nepal has yet to ratify the Rome Statute, also known as the International Criminal Code, which is considered a crucial legal instrument for safeguarding human rights. This statute provides an avenue for justice at the international level when a country's domestic laws fail to deliver justice to its citizens. Given this, Nepal should consider ratifying the Rome Statute, which was drafted on July 17, 1998, signed the following day, and came into force on July 1, 2002. Despite being signed by 139 countries and ratified by 118, Nepal's political leaders have shown little interest in ratifying it thus far. However, human rights organizations have been actively advocating for its ratification. It is argued that

Nepal's international reputation could benefit from a proactive approach to ratifying the Rome Statute. Therefore, it is imperative for Nepal to consider ratifying the Rome Statute promptly.

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